

Effects of Size, Steric Hindrance and Basicity of Primary Ligand on the Solution Stability of Binary and Ternary Complexes of Zinc(II) with some Amino Acids and Acetic Acid. A Voltammetric Approach

FARID KHAN* and KRISHNA NEMA

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 24 August 1989, revised 11 February 1991, accepted 23 April 1991

THE present paper describes a voltammetric study of mixed ligand complex formation of zinc(II) with some amino acids, viz. glycine, α -alanine, L-leucine, L-valine, L-glutamine and L-asparagine as primary ligands and acetic acid as secondary ligand.

Exeperimental

A.R. grade chemical were used to prepare all the solutions in double-distilled water. The Zn^{II} solution was standardised by E D.T.A. method¹ and the purity of amino acids was checked by chromatographic method². The concentrations of Zn, potassium nitrate and gelatin in the experimental solutions were 1.0 mM, 1.0M and 0.001% respectively.

Current-voltage measurements were made on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal PL-50 polyflex galvanometer having capillary characteristics $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.0 cm (60.02 calculated)³ effective height of mercury. pH measurements were made on a Elico LI-10 pH meter. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The pH value of the test solutions was adjusted with dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and nitric acid

as required. Zinc and ligands were mixed in ratios 1 : 40 and 1 : 40 : 40 and current-voltage curves were drawn at different pH values. The maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ values was obtained at $\text{pH } 8.50 \pm 0.1$ and hence this pH was selected for the present study.

Results and Discussion

Zinc(II) gave well-defined two-electron reversible reduction wave in 1.0 M KNO₃. The nature of waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled which were clear from $E_{d.o}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ and i_d vs $\sqrt{t}$ plots. The polarograms of Zn^{II}, Zn-acetate and Zn-glycinat-acetate systems are given in Fig. 1. For binary systems, the values of stability constants were determined by Lingane⁶ and DeFord and Hume⁷ methods, whereas the Schaap and McMaster⁸ method was used for the mixed ligand complexes.

Fig. 1. Polarograms in 1.0 M KNO₃: (a) Zn^{II}, (b) [Zn-acetate] in the ratio 1 : 40 and (c) [Zn-glycinat-acetate] in the ratio 1 : 10 : 10.

Zinc-acetate system : This system was studied at $\text{pH} = 8.50 \pm 0.1$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M KNO}_3$. The concentration of the ligand was varied from 0.01 to 0.1 M at 0.001% gelatin used as maximum suppressor. All the waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled. Lingane⁶ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The stability constants values are stated in Table 1.

Zinc-amino acids-acetate systems : The pK values of amino acids were determined by titration method⁹ and are given in Table 1. The present study was carried out at pK_1^H values of amino acids. The $E_{1/2}$ values of (Zn-amino acids) systems increased with the increase of concentration of acetate

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF ZINC(II) WITH AMINO ACIDS AND ACETIC ACID

Ligand	Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M (KNO}_3)$		$\log \beta_{01}$	$\log \beta_{02}$	$\log \beta_{10}$	$\log \beta_{20}$	$\log \beta_{30}$	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
	pK_1^H	pK_2^H								
Glycine	9.30	2.40	—	—	4.80	8.94	11.41	6.54	9.28	10.75
α -Alanine	9.40	2.50	—	—	4.73	8.80	11.22	6.38	9.06	10.53
L-Leucine	9.71	2.28	—	—	4.50	8.72	11.03	6.33	8.79	10.38
L-Valine	9.74	2.32	—	—	4.43	8.58	10.84	6.17	8.57	10.16
L-Asparagine	9.13	2.17	—	—	4.40	8.52	10.43	6.13	8.48	9.83
L-Glutamine	8.80	2.02	—	—	4.38	8.38	10.24	5.97	8.26	9.61
Acetic acid	—	—	2.40	3.92	—	—	—	—	—	—

ions indicating the formation of mixed ligand complexes. The concentration of primary ligand, i.e. amino acid varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM while the concentration of secondary ligand, i.e. acetic acid was kept constant at 0.005 and 0.01 M and current-voltage curves were drawn. The nature of waves was reversible and diffusion-controlled. Schaap and McMaster⁷ method confirmed the formation of 1:1:1, 1:2:1 and 1:1:2 [Zn^{II}-amino acid-acetate] complexes. Values of stability constant were given in Table 1.

The trends of stability constants with respect to binary and ternary complexes were L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α-alanine < glycine. Remarkable changes due to size, basicity and steric hindrance of amino acids on the stability constants were observed. It was found that if the length of side-chain in amino acid is increased, the stability constant of binary complexes decreased by a constant factor definitively $\log \beta_{RSB^*}$, i.e. $[Zn(\alpha\text{-ala})]^+$, $[Zn(\alpha\text{-ala})_2]$ and $[Zn(\alpha\text{-ala})_3]^-$ have lesser stabilities than $[Zn(\text{gly})]^+$, $[Zn(\text{gly})_2]$ and $[Zn(\text{gly})_3]^-$ by $\log \beta_{RSB_{10}} = 0.0694$, $\log \beta_{RSB_{20}} = 0.1333$ and $\log \beta_{RSB_{30}} = 0.1875$, respectively. Similar effect was also observed in the complexes of Zn^{II} with other amino acids, except in the case of L-valine and L-leucine where the order was reversed, i.e. L-valine < L-leucine. This is due to the fact that in L-valine, the isopropyl group lies at α-carbon atom, whereas it is at β-carbon atom in case of L-leucine, therefore the steric hindrance is higher in the former than in the later, causing the lesser stability of the L-valine complexes than the L-leucine complexes. This reversal order of stability constants is also due to the higher basicity of L-leucine than L-valine.

In the ternary complexes, the stabilities of $[Zn(\alpha\text{-ala})(\text{acet})]$, $[Zn(\alpha\text{-ala})_2(\text{acet})]^-$ and $[Zn(\alpha\text{-ala})(\text{acet})_2]^-$ systems were lower than those of $[Zn(\text{gly})(\text{acet})]$, $[Zn(\text{gly})_2(\text{acet})]^-$ and $[Zn(\text{gly})(\text{acet})_2]^-$ by a constant factor $\log \beta_{RST}^{**}$, i.e. $\log \beta_{RST_{11}} = 0.16$, $\log \beta_{RST_{21}} = 0.2222$ and $\log \beta_{RST_{12}} = 0.2222$, respectively.

$$* \frac{(Z+4)im}{12(Z+5)} = \log \beta_{RSB}$$

$$\text{and } ** \frac{(Z+4)(i+j)m}{10(Z+5)} = \log \beta_{RST}$$

where, Z stands for charge on the complex and i, j and m are the stoichiometric numbers for primary ligand, secondary ligand and metal ion, respectively, represent the complexation equilibria,

$\log \beta_{RSB}$ reduction factor, gives the reduction in stability for binary complexes when side-chain in amino acid is increased by CH₂ and $\log \beta_{RST}$ reduction factor decreases the stability constants for ternary complexes when the side-chain in primary ligand is (i.e. amino acid) increased by CH₂.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. P. Banerjee, Professor, Head and Dean of Faculty of Sciences,

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, for facilities and to M. P. University Grants Commission for providing a Fellowship to one of them (K.N.).

References

1. A. J. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd, ed., Longmans, London, 1978, p. 680.
2. A. A. KHAN and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 566.
3. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Technique", 2nd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 131.
4. C. J. NYMAN, E. W. MURBACH and G. B. MILLARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 4194.
5. D. R. CROW, "Polarography of Metal Complexes", Academic, London, 1969, p. 27.
6. J. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941 29, 1.
7. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5312.
8. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4699.
9. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5052.
10. L. E. MALEY and D. P. MELLOR, *Nature*, 1950, 165, 453.